

Gold Price Prediction using Machine Learning

Tebin Joseph
Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirapally, India
tebinjoseph20220b@mca.ajce.in

Anit James
Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirapally, India
anitjames@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract — Gold price prediction is a research area in which both business professionals and academics have been involved for a long time, traditional prediction models based on linear regression and statistical models are available in the literature, but the efficiency of the models needs to be improved and the application of artificial and machine learning needs to be applied for the accuracy of the predictions

Keywords— Gold price , Forecasting, Machine learning Algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the physical worth of gold, it is regarded as a safe asset in comparison to other currencies, and investors have flocked to gold assets in times of market turmoil since ancient times. The primary uses of gold, apart from its investment value, are in terms of its high use in the fine jewelry, electronics and high-tech industries where it is used as a high-quality conductive material for the manufacture of printed circuit boards and semiconductor components. Recently due to the global economic recession brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic, investors are flocking to buy gold related assets because global currencies are rapidly losing value and are very volatile. In this scenario, gold price forecasting is of paramount importance from both a business and academic perspective as it will enable financial practitioners to predict the future financial situation. Anticipating the rise and fall in daily gold prices can help investors decide when to buy (or sell) the commodity. But gold prices depend on many factors like other precious metals prices, crude oil prices, stock exchange performance, bond prices, currency exchange rates etc. In this project, we will use the most comprehensive set of features to estimate gold prices, and we will use various machine learning algorithms to predict the results. Gold is one of the commodities traded on the global financial markets, and it is regarded as an asset that preserves its actual worth despite currency depreciation. Machine learning techniques are required to detect the user.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Shafiee, S., Topal,, Yimin Policy 35(3). The study validates the model and anticipates the gold price for the next 10 years using monthly historical data for the nominal gold price.

Navin, G.V. Int. J. Sci. Res. (IJSR) 4(3) Develop a gold price forecasting model based on economic elements such as inflation, currency price changes, and other considerations. Investors put their money into the market

to make a profit, their money in gold because gold plays an important role as a stabilizing factor for investment portfolios.

Weng, F., et al vol.16.01, pp. 205–223(2017). The volatility of gold prices is of great importance to avoid the risks of investing in gold. It is necessary to understand the impact of external events and the essential regularity that needs to be done Accurate price predictions.

Hafezi, R., Akhavan Model Simul. 50(1),71–82(2018). Predicting price fluctuations is a major concern in financial markets. Thus, developing an accurate and robust forecast decision model is critical for investors. Since gold has shown a special ability to smooth down the fluctuations of inflation, conservatives use gold as a tool to control prices.

Ur Sami, I., Junejo, K.N. Appl. 8(12) 92–99 (2017). Historically, gold, along with other payment systems, was used to fund trade transactions all over the world. Various countries have kept and increased their gold reserves, and they have been seen as wealthy and forward-thinking nations. Currently, all countries' central banks hold precious metals such as gold to assure the repayment of external obligations.

III. MOTIVATION

Forecasting prices is an important aspect of the economy decision making. Forecasts can be applied in a wide variety of ways. Individuals may use predictions to try to gain money from speculative activities, to decide the best government policies, or to make economic decisions, among other things. The purpose of this study was to develop a model for forecasting gold prices using economic factors such as exchange rate fluctuations and other variables.

IV . METHODOLOGY

According to the literature review, powerful and versatile machine learning models for application in the financial sphere are needed to improve gold price prediction models. The major goals of this research are to create a machine learning model with the ability to employ both decision rules and regression outputs to calculate the price of gold. Training on historical data is required, as well as validation utilizing real-time input. The structure is as follows:

Figure 1: Gold Price Prediction Methodology

The steps that require to be followed are:

1. Data Collection
2. Data Pre-processing
3. Choosing Model
4. Training Model
5. Prediction

A. Data Collection: The user has a gold price dataset, and the properties of this dataset are used to train the model. The data is the first item that must be provided when creating a machine learning model. The information was gathered via Kaggle. The website has 45 records and seven themes.

B. Data Pre-processing: When the data is incomplete, inconsistent, or unsettling, pre-processing is essential. We ran an external analysis and deleted the noisy data because the data collected was noisy. The data is also altered through normalization, which involves measuring the data in each characteristic. Data cleansing, data transformation, and data minimization are all part of this process. All of this is done to improve the data's effectiveness.

The data can be processed to make our model more accurate. So that the classification will be correct.

a. Cleaning Data – The data is initially cleaned. This here users remove unwanted entries. Noisy data can also be removed from the dataset.

b. Removing Stop words – The stop words are removed from the data sets. These are the most visible and which do not have much significance in the text. To achieve more accuracy of the model this can be done.

c. Splitting of Data – After the data is cleaned, the data is divided into training and test datasets. The data selected for training is then used to train our model.

C. Machine Learning: The linear Holt method, commonly known as double exponential smoothing, is the prediction algorithm employed. The term "double exponential smoothing" refers to a extension of "single exponential smoothing."

Single Exponential Smoothing (SES) is a prediction technique used with univariate data, and ES assumes that the data has no trend or seasonality/periodicity. SES uses a weighted sum of past observations to make predictions. As the notes get older, their weight drops dramatically. The only parameter of SES is α , which is known as the smoothing coefficient. The value of Alpha ranges between 0 and 1, and it controls the rate of decay of the previous observations.

SES formula: $y_t = \alpha x_t + (1 - \alpha) y_{t-1}$

Note: α : smoothing factor, t: time period

Double exponential smoothing differs from SES because it adds a trend component. This makes double exponential smoothing appropriate when trends are present in a time series Double exponential smoothing techniques are commonly used in marketing and finance to make short-term forecasts on time series with trend.

Double exponential smoothing additive method forecast formula: $\hat{y}_{t+n} = l_t + nb_t$

- Level formula: $l_t = (1 - \alpha) l_{t-1} + \alpha x_t$
- Trend formula: $b_t = (1 - \beta) b_{t-1} + \beta (l_t - l_{t-1})$
- Model formula: $y_{t+n} = l_t + b_t$

Notation: α : level smoothing constant, β : trend smoothing constant, t: observed time units, n: number of time units to be predicted for

Double exponential smoothing additive method forecast formula: $\hat{y}_{t+n} = l_t + (\phi^1 + \phi^2 + \phi^h) nb_t$

- Level formula: $l_t = (1 - \alpha) l_{t-1} + \alpha x_t$
- Trend formula: $b_t = (1 - \beta) b_{t-1} + \beta (l_t - l_{t-1})$
- Model formula: $y_{t+n} = l_t + b_t$

Notation: α : level smoothing constant, β : trend smoothing constant, t: observed time units, n: number of time units to predict, ϕ : damming coefficient

V. BUILD MODEL

1. The item's name and the data's placement in the user's directory. This is the default configuration for both the system and the server. All of the necessary packages should be imported.

```
[2] from google.colab import files
    uploaded = files.upload()

Choose files: gold_final_rate.csv
• gold_final_rate.csv(text/csv) - 2901 bytes, last modified: 6/8/2022 - 100% done
Saving gold_final_rate.csv to gold_final_rate.csv
```

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np

gold = pd.read_csv(r"gold_final_rate.csv")
# print(gold)
display(gold.head(10))
```

2. Add the data into a Data Frame, then get the shape of data.

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np

gold = pd.read_csv(r"gold_final_rate.csv")
# print(gold)
display(gold.head(10))
```

```
gold = pd.read_csv(r"gold_final_rate.csv")
# print(gold)
display(gold.head(7))
```

	Date	USD	EUR	GBP	INR	AED	CNY
0	1978	193.44	124.73580	100.65449	2470.00000	1162.00000	926.64518
1	1979	304.68	185.06142	143.09014	2481.90512	1163.93597	1272.38854
2	1980	614.50	378.19461	263.80259	4831.74943	2278.36795	1659.60015
3	1981	459.26	360.90588	227.01948	3966.64790	1691.03194	1626.12034
4	1982	375.30	345.59742	215.53232	3553.62680	1378.72895	1434.30585
5	1983	423.66	439.89318	279.24936	4270.42821	1557.45790	1827.11273
6	1984	360.78	425.91000	269.81553	4067.60433	1324.72272	1170.00000

3. We're only interested in the INR gold prices, so we'll drop the other currency columns.

```
[4] # print(gold)
    gold = gold[["Date", "INR"]]

    gold.index = gold["Date"]
    gold = gold.drop(columns=["Date"])
    gold.index = pd.to_datetime(gold.index, format="%Y")
    gold.index.freq = gold.index.inferred_freq
```

4. Using summary statistics and graphical representations, we use exploratory data analysis to test hypotheses and validate assumptions.

```
[5] import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

plt.figure(figsize=(12,6))
plt.plot(gold.index, gold["INR"])
plt.title("Annual Gold Price")
plt.xlabel("Date")
plt.ylabel("Price")
plt.grid()
plt.show()
```

5. We will use STL analysis to look for anomalies in the data.

```
pip install statsmodels==0.12.1
```

6. For the model, we will use the Holt linear trend method (double exponential smoothing) as the data appears to have a large variance.

```
[9] from statsmodels.tsa.holtwinters import ExponentialSmoothing
    print (gold.iloc[31:])
    train = gold.iloc[:31]
    test = gold.iloc[31:]

    holts = ExponentialSmoothing(train, trend="add")
    holts_fit = holts.fit(optimized=True)
    train_pred = holts_fit.predict(start=0)
    test_pred = holts_fit.forecast((len(gold)-len(train)))
    print(test_pred)
```

7. Then we analyze the observed and predicted plot

```

from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error
from math import sqrt

#observed vs predicted
plt.figure(figsize=(15,6))
plt.plot(train_pred, color="darkgreen", label="predicted train", ls="--")
plt.plot(test_pred, color="crimson", label="predicted test", ls="--")
plt.plot(train, color="blue", label="train")
plt.plot(test, color="orange", label="test")
plt.title("Observed vs. Predicted Train/Test Gold Price (INR) per Ounce")
plt.legend()
plt.show()

mse = mean_squared_error(test, test_pred)
scatter_index = (sqrt(mse))/(test.mean())[0].round(3)
print("Scatter Index:", scatter_index)
    
```

8. Gives out the forecasted graph .

```

#forecast
forecast = holts_fit.forecast((len(gold)-len(train))+20)
plt.figure(figsize=(15,6))
plt.plot(gold.index, gold["INR"], color="black", label="Observed")
plt.plot(forecast[(len(gold)-len(train)):], color="green", ls="--", label="Forecasted")
plt.title("Forecasted Annual Gold Price (INR) per Ounce")
plt.legend()
plt.show()

print(forecast[(len(gold)-len(train)):])
    
```

VI . RESULT

The result shows that the Gold Price can be predicted based on the dataset given. The Holt linear trend method provides proper result with high accuracy. The dataset contain gold price from different areas that are in USD, INR, EUR, AED . This is categorized, and the algorithm properly detected the Gold Rate, resulting in a predicted price per 31.1gm of 24 carat gold.

Predicted Output :

```

2022-01-01    122097.706537
2023-01-01    128230.322513
2024-01-01    134362.938489
2025-01-01    140495.554466
2026-01-01    146628.170442
2027-01-01    152760.786418
2028-01-01    158893.402394
2029-01-01    165026.018370
2030-01-01    171158.634347
2031-01-01    177291.250323
Freq: AS-JAN, dtype: float64
    
```

VII . CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to develop the current prediction Knowledge-based models and gold prices to make them accurate enough to be used in real-life scenarios. A literature review revealed that price prediction models use traditional linear regression models and have also applied machine learning models such as Hot's linear trend method.

A review of the literature also reveals that versatility A model that can combine qualitative aspects such as domain-specific rules and quantitative outputs such as nonlinear regression must be combined to create an accurate prediction. The model developed here is able to accurately predict gold prices and will certainly help commodity investors in reducing their losses by means of the excellent forecasting available with this model.

VIII.REFERENCES

- [1] Shafiee, S., Topal, E: Global gold market overview and gold price forecasting. *Resor. Politics* 35 (3), 178–189 (2010).
- [2] Navin, G.V: Big Data Analytics for Gold Price Prediction based on Decision Tree Algorithm and Support Vector Regression (SVR). *Int J. Sci. Precision. (IJSR)* 4 (3) (2015).
- [3] Wen, F., et al: Multi-scale volatility characteristic analysis and gold price forecasting. In: *International Journal of Information Technology and Decision Making*, Vol. 16.01, pp. 205-223 (2017).
- [4] Hafezi, R., Akhavan, A: Predicting changes in gold prices: an application of an equipped artificial neural network. *AUT Model J. Simulation.* 50 (1), 71-82 (2018).
- [5] Ur Sami, I, Junejo, K.N: Predicting future gold prices using a machine learning approach. *Int J Adv. computer. Sciences. Application* 8 (12) 92-99 (2017).